

Reaction of Phenyl Tetrachlorophosphorane with Arylidencyanoacetamides

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Phenyl tetrachlorophosphorane reacts with arylidencyanoacetamides to give N-(arylidencyanoacetyl)phosphonimidic dichlorides (1-5). The nitrile group of the latter is not affected by excess phenyl tetrachlorophosphorane under different experimental conditions. 1-5 are not stable to atmospheric moisture and easily hydrolyze to the corresponding phosphonamidic chloride (6-10). The latter compounds are easily obtained by acetolysis or formolysis. The structures of (1-10) are supported by their infrared spectra. The ultraviolet spectra of the compounds (1-10) have been measured.

In an earlier study¹, it was found that, phosphorus pentachloride reacted with arylidene cyanoacetamides to give N-(2-arylidene-2-cyanoacetyl)phosphorimidic trichlorides, in agreement with Kirsanov reaction².

In the present investigation we describe the reaction of phenyl tetrachlorophosphorane, $C_6H_5PCl_4$, with arylidencyanoacetamides, compare its reactivity with that of phosphorus pentachloride and study the chemistry of the derived products.

In the case of PCl_5 the reaction was carried out in boiling benzene (80°) and lasted only for 20 min. Phenyl tetrachlorophosphorane on the other hand reacts more slowly. The reaction mixture should be heated for 30-60 min., in boiling benzene for carbon tetrachloride.

Compound	Ar
1	C_6H_5
2	$p\text{-ClC}_6H_4$
3	$m\text{-NO}_2\text{-C}_6H_4$
4	$p\text{-NO}_2\text{-C}_6H_4$
5	$p\text{-CH}_3\text{O-C}_6H_4$

It was reported by Kirsanov³ that the hydrogen chloride which is evolved in the reaction of benzamide with halogeno phosphorus compounds catalyzes the splitting of the phosphimine into benzonitrile

and the phosphorus oxyhalide. For rapid removal of the hydrogen chloride formed, the author recommended to carry out the reaction in a vacuum of 150-200 mm. Under these conditions, the phosphazo compounds were obtained in higher yield and in a purer state.

However, we found that, compounds (1-5) can be obtained without rapid removal of hydrogen chloride from the reaction mixture as they are stable in the presence of hydrogen chloride.

The nitrile group or the ethylenic hydrogen of arylidencyanoacetamides was not affected by excess (threefold or more) phenyl tetrachlorophosphorane, under different experimental conditions.

The structure of compounds (1-5) was inferred from a study of their infrared spectra. These spectra showed an absorption band at 1280 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to the stretching frequency of $N=P$ linkage⁴. The absorption band at 2220 cm^{-1} is attributed to the stretching frequency of the $C\equiv N$ group, although the intensity is low, but this is to be expected in the compounds having in the α -position to the nitrile group a strong electron attracting group⁵. The ultraviolet spectra show maxima at 260-340 nm (cf. Table 2). N-(Arylidencyanoacetyl) phenyl phosphonimidic dichlorides (1-5) are colorless to faint yellow crystalline compounds, insoluble in petroleum ether, soluble in boiling benzene or carbon tetrachloride. In boiling chlorobenzene they decompose to give benzyldenemalonitriles and phenylphosphonic dichloride.

TABLE 1—N-(ARYLIDENE CYANOACETYL) PHENYL PHOSPHONIMIDIC DICHLORIDES AND N-(ARYLIDENE CYANOACETYL) PHENYL PHOSPHONAMIDIC CHLORIDE

No.	Yield %	m.p. °C	Found			Formula	Calculated		
			N	Cl	P		N	Cl	P
1	80	108—110	8.00	20.11	8.72	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ OP	8.02	20.34	8.88
2	75	140—142	7.12	27.57	7.99	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₃ N ₂ OP	7.30	27.77	8.08
3	72	170—172	10.41	17.98	7.81	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₃ P	10.66	18.02	7.87
4	78	180—181	10.54	17.81	7.79	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₃ P	10.66	18.02	7.87
5	82	138—140	7.15	18.54	8.00	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ P	7.39	18.73	8.18
6	74	150—152	8.35	10.52	9.29	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClN ₂ O ₂ P	8.47	10.74	9.38
7	82	179—180	7.54	19.32	8.37	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂ P	7.67	19.45	8.49
8	85	183—185	11.00	9.39	8.21	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₃ O ₄ P	11.19	9.45	8.26
9	80	188—189	10.98	9.29	8.15	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ClN ₃ O ₄ P	11.19	9.45	8.26
10	83	138—140	7.68	9.69	8.54	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₃ P	7.77	9.85	8.60

They are easily hydrolyzed even by moisture to give N-(arylidene cyanoacetyl)phenylphosphonamidic chloride (6-10).

Compound	R
6	H
7	<i>p</i> -Cl
8	<i>m</i> -NO ₂
9	<i>p</i> -NO ₂
10	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃

If the hydrolysis is carried out in the presence of excess water, the N-(arylidene cyanoacetyl)phenylphosphonamide chlorides initially formed are further hydrolysed to give benzylidene cyanoacetamides and phenylphosphonic acid.

The phosphonamidic chlorides (6-10) can also be obtained by the action of formic or acetic acids on

the phosphonimidic chlorides (1-5) as has been generally mentioned for phosphinimine compounds [1].

The use of formic acid is generally preferred because its acid chloride decomposes into HCl and CO which are gases that immediately evolve as soon as they are formed, leaving the products of formolysis in a pure form.

The phosphonamidic chlorides (6-10) are crystalline compounds soluble in hot chloroform, carbon-tetrachloride and benzene and insoluble in petroleum ether. The infrared spectra of these compounds show bands at 1265-1280 cm⁻¹ and 3180-3200 cm⁻¹ due to P = O and NH stretching vibrations.

The ultraviolet spectra of compounds (6-10) show maxima at 260-340 nm (cf. Table 2).

TABLE 2—ULTRAVIOLET SPECTRAL DATA—8 COMPOUNDS 1-10.

Com- pound	max. mμ	max.10 ⁻⁴	Com- pound	max. mμ	max.10 ⁻⁴
1	325	2.8	6	324	2.5
2	331	1.66	7	333	1.36
3	303	1.96	8	303	2.1
4	315	1.22	9	315	1.1
5	255	6.65	10	255	5.9

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Microanalysis were carried out by El-Nasr Pharmaceutical Chemical Company.

Infrared Spectra were measured on a Unicam SP 200 G Spectrophotometer and Ultraviolet absorption spectra with Beckman DK-2A. Arylidene-cyanoacetamides are known and prepared according to the procedure cited in the literature⁶. Because of the moisture sensitivity of the phenyl tetrachlorophosphorane and its derivatives all sample transfers were made in a controlled atmosphere box at low humidities.

N-(Arylidene-cyanoacetyl) phenyl phosphonimidic dichlorides (1-5) :

To a solution of 0.01 mole of phenyl tetrachlorophosphorane in 50 ml. carbon tetrachloride placed in a round-bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser with an outlet to a water pump, was gradually added a mixture of 0.01 mole of arylidene-cyanoacetamide and 10 ml. carbon tetrachloride. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 40-60 min., whereupon all the amide dissolved. The carbon tetrachloride was distilled off in a vacuum to 1/3 the original volume. The crystals which precipitated was filtered off, washed with ether (2×5 ml.) and dried. It was recrystallised from dry benzene (see Table 1).

N-(Arylidene-cyanoacetyl) phenyl phosphonamidic chlorides (5-10) :

To a solution of 0.01 mol. in 50 ml. benzene, was added gradually 0.01 mole of anhydrous formic acid

and the mixture allowed to stand for 4 to 6 hrs at room temperature. The benzene was distilled off in a vacuum to 1/3 the original volume. The crystals which precipitated was filtered off, washed with benzene (2×5 ml.) and dried. It was recrystallised from dry benzene (see Table 1).

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